

Evaluation of novel data-driven metrics of amyloid β deposition for longitudinal PET studies

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Positron emission tomography (PET) provides *in vivo* quantification of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) pathology. Established methods for assessing $A\beta$ burden can be affected by physiological and technical factors. Novel, data-driven metrics have been developed to account for these sources of variability. We aimed to evaluate the performance of four of these amyloid PET metrics against conventional techniques, using a common set of criteria. **Methods:** Three cohorts were used for evaluation: Insight 46 ($N=464$, [^{18}F]florbetapir), AIBL ($N=277$, [^{18}F]flutemetamol), and an independent test-retest data ($N=10$, [^{18}F]flutemetamol). Established metrics of amyloid tracer uptake included the Centiloid (CL) and where dynamic data was available, the non-displaceable binding potential (BP_{ND}). The four data-driven metrics computed were the amyloid load ($A\beta$ load), the $A\beta$ -PET pathology accumulation index ($A\beta$ index), the Centiloid derived from non-negative matrix factorisation (CL_{NMF}), and the amyloid pattern similarity score (AMPSS). These metrics were evaluated using reliability and repeatability in test-retest data, associations with BP_{ND} and CL, variability of the rate of change and sample size estimates to detect a 25% slowing in $A\beta$ accumulation.

Results: All metrics showed good reliability. $A\beta$ load, $A\beta$ index and CL_{NMF} were strongly associated with the BP_{ND} . The associations with CL suggest that cross-sectional measures of CL_{NMF} , $A\beta$ index and $A\beta$ load are robust across studies. Sample size estimates for secondary prevention trial scenarios were the lowest for CL_{NMF} and $A\beta$ load compared to the CL.

Conclusion: Among the novel data-driven metrics evaluated, the $A\beta$ load, the $A\beta$ index and the CL_{NMF} can provide comparable performance to more established quantification methods of $A\beta$ PET tracer uptake. The CL_{NMF} and $A\beta$ load could offer a more precise alternative to CL, although further studies in larger cohorts should be conducted.

Abbreviations: AD, Alzheimer's disease; ADNI, Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative; AIBL, Australian Imaging Biomarkers and Lifestyle Study of Ageing; AMPSS, amyloid pattern similarity score; $A\beta$ index, $A\beta$ -PET pathology accumulation index; ARC, annualised rate of change; BP_{ND} , non-displaceable binding potential; CL, Centiloid; CL_{NMF} , Centiloid scale based on non-negative matrix factorisation; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; DARTEL, diffeomorphic anatomical registration through exponentiated lie algebra; DVR, distribution volume ratio; GAAIN, Global Alzheimer's Association Interactive Network; GIF, geodesic information flow; ICC, intraclass correlation coefficient; K, amyloid carrying capacity; LME, linear mixed effects models; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; MNI, Montreal Neurological Institute; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; NifTI, Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative; NS, non-specific binding; p.i., post injection; PCA, principal component analysis; PET, positron emission tomography; ROI, region of interest; SMC, subjective memory complaint; SUVr, standardized uptake value ratio; SVM, support vector machine.

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1. Introduction

Longitudinal Positron Emission Tomography (PET) studies measuring the rate of change in amyloid and tau burden can provide a better understanding of the earliest stages and subsequent spread of Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathology. Measuring small spatiotemporal changes in protein deposition with high accuracy and precision can facilitate early detection and tracking of the disease (Ortner et al., 2019), increase the prognostic value by determining the risk of cognitive decline (Hanseeuw et al., 2019), and better inform clinical trial design (Lopes Alves et al., 2021). PET-based imaging endpoints are particularly relevant for regulatory approval of anti-amyloid therapies as disease modifying treatments (Cummings and Salloway, 2021, Budd Haeberlein et al., 2022), and especially useful for trials in early or preclinical AD populations such as the AHEAD 3-45 study (Klein et al., 2019, Aisen et al., 2020, Mintun et al., 2021, Rafi et al., 2022). In clinical practice, quantification plays a supplemental role in assisting visual reads of scans in the earliest stages of pathological build-up, where there is lower confidence in image interpretation (Bucci et al., 2021). When disease-modifying therapies become more widely available, quantification might also help response monitoring with more precision than a discrete visual rating scale (Pemberton et al., 2022), and support treatment efficacy decisions (Lopes Alves et al., 2020).

The accuracy and precision of PET data quantification is influenced by the measure used to determine the cortical amyloid β ($A\beta$) burden and rate of accumulation. Quantitative PET measurements based on kinetic modelling of fully dynamic acquisitions can best account for specific and non-specific contributions to tracer uptake. Although the non-displaceable binding potential (BP_{ND}) derived from those measurements is considered the most accurate in the absence of histopathology, the lengthy and costly acquisition it requires is often not feasible. Thus, the most common technique to measure amyloid burden is the standardized uptake value ratio (SUVr) using shorter static acquisitions at a pre-determined period post-injection, where the tracer is assumed to have reached pseudo-equilibrium. The SUVr corresponds to the ratio between the average uptake of the radiotracer in a target region of interest (ROI) and a reference region which is assumed to have no specific tracer uptake. To mitigate biases and variabilities attributed to various tracer effects, the Centiloid (CL) scale was introduced as a means of calibrating measures of amyloid burden to a tracer-independent, unbounded scale where 0 (PET signal characteristic of young healthy controls) and 100 (typical AD subjects) serve as anchor points. The calibration that the CL scale offers may be advantageous for multi-centre and multi-tracer studies (Klunk et al., 2015).

However, semi-quantitative measures obtained with SUVr and CL can be affected by a wide range of additional biological and technical sources of error and variability (Schmidt et al., 2015). In particular, the choice of reference region is a recurrent subject of debate as the tracer used, the stability and the definition of the reference region significantly affect the amyloid signal over time (Barthel et al., 2015, Bullich et al., 2017, Cho et al., 2020, Heeman et al., 2020). Accurate spatial definition of the ROIs relies on the quality of the segmentation, and in particular its ability to capture an accurate sampling of non-specific uptake. Finally, some reference regions have also shown evidence of amyloid pathology in specific forms of AD, such as cerebellar $A\beta$ plaques in autosomal dominant forms of AD (Ghisays et al., 2021).

To alleviate some of these concerns, four novel data-driven methods for measuring $A\beta$ deposits have been proposed:

- The amyloid load ($A\beta$ load) developed by Whittington and Gunn is based on image decomposition to extract the specific tracer binding. This decomposition is based upon characterising the SUVr trajectory over the disease course with a logistic growth model, assuming unique maximum amyloid carrying capacity for each brain region (Whittington and Gunn, 2019).

- The $A\beta$ -PET pathology accumulation index ($A\beta$ index) by Leuzy et al. relies on a principal component analysis (PCA) approach where one component, representing the tracer specific binding to $A\beta$ is estimated as part of a registration process between a new image and an adaptive group template (Leuzy et al., 2020).
- The improved Centiloid scale (CL_{NMF}) developed by Bourgeat et al., uses non-negative matrix factorisation (NMF), another type of image decomposition, to generate a metric less susceptible to tracer-related changes in longitudinal studies compared to the original CL scale (Bourgeat et al., 2021).
- The Amyloid Pattern Similarity Score (AMPSS) proposes a classifier-based approach that uses a support vector machine (SVM) to identify the multivariate patterns of amyloid burden, and produces a probabilistic score reflecting this burden relative to a reference population (Prosser et al., 2020).

These four metrics have been developed using independent datasets and validated using different sets of evaluation criteria, such as agreement with the SUVr and histopathology, or precision in detecting changes over time. However, there has yet to be a systematic validation of these novel data-driven metrics using consistent data and evaluation criteria. This study aims to evaluate these data-driven metrics based on their performance against metrics established in the literature, in terms of repeatability, reliability, association with BP_{ND} and CL, variability of the rate of change and sample size requirements to power clinical trials. These assessments have been conducted using two longitudinal datasets and a test-retest dataset. In addition, we also considered the advantages and limitations in the implementations of those metrics to best assess how they could help capture small changes in protein deposition over time.

2. Materials & methods

The four data-driven approaches that were considered are described below: the $A\beta$ load (Whittington and Gunn, 2019), the $A\beta$ index (Leuzy et al., 2020), the CL_{NMF} (Bourgeat et al., 2021), and the AMPSS (Prosser et al., 2020) (key concepts detailed in Supplementary material). To simplify the evaluation of these metrics, we summarised the main implementation steps and harmonised the nomenclature around the different aspects of these methods (see Fig. 1). A comparative overview of the different methods can be found in Table 1.

2.1. Data acquisition

Data from three separate cohorts was used (see Table 2).

2.1.1. Insight46

First, 350 subjects from Insight46, a prospective neuroscience sub-study of the MRC National Survey of Health and Development (Lane et al., 2017), with baseline and follow-up dynamic PET-MR scans (follow-up time: 2.4 ± 0.2 years) acquired with [^{18}F]florbetapir were included. All study members were born in the same week of 1946. The majority were cognitively normal.

Images were acquired on the same Biograph mMR 3T PET/MRI scanner (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen). The full study protocol is described elsewhere (Lane et al., 2017). In short, 370 MBq of [^{18}F]florbetapir was injected intravenously. PET data were acquired continuously for ~60 minutes from the time of injection to allow both full kinetic modelling and static analysis during the last ~10 min of scanning (from 50 to 60 min). Both static and dynamic data were acquired in list-mode and reconstructed offline via a 3D OSEM algorithm with three iterations and 21 subsets, using the software NiftyPET (Markiewicz et al., 2018). Attenuation correction was based on a pseudo-CT synthesis from T1 and T2 weighted MR images (Burgos et al., 2014, Ladefoged et al., 2017). The dynamic acquisition consisted of 31 frames (4×15 seconds, 8×30 seconds, 9×60 seconds, 2×180 seconds, and 8×300 seconds).

Images were smoothed with a 4mm Gaussian kernel with no partial volume correction and were then used as inputs for the image processing and analysis pipelines.

2.1.2. AIBL

We included 277 subjects from the Australian Imaging, Biomarkers and Lifestyle (AIBL) flagship study of aging with PET scans acquired at up to three timepoints using [¹⁸F]flutemetamol (Ellis et al., 2009). The

Aβ_L = Aβ load (Whittington and Gunn, *J Nucl Med*, 2019)

Aβ index = Aβ pathology accumulation index (Leuzy et al., *Neurology*, 2020)

CL_{NMF} = Centiloid derived from non-negative matrix factorisation (Bourgeat et al., *Neuroimage*, 2021)

AMPSS = amyloid pattern similarity score (Prosser et al., *AAIC*, 2020)

Fig. 1. Key concepts behind four novel metrics of amyloid deposition.

Abbreviations – SUVr: standardized uptake value ratio; Ref. reg.: reference region used for SUVr computation; cgm: cerebellar grey matter reference region; whc: whole cerebellum reference region; PC: principal component; NS: non-specific; K: amyloid carrying capacity; NMF: non-negative matrix factorisation.

Table 1
Overview of four data-driven metrics of A β deposition.

Main characteristics	A β load <i>Whittington et al., 2019</i>	A β index <i>Leuzy et al., 2020</i>	CL _{NMF} <i>Bourgeat et al., 2021</i>	AMPSS <i>Prosser et al., 2020</i>
Key idea	Image decomposition into 2 components: non-specific binding and A β carrying capacity determined via logistic growth model	Image decomposition via principal component analysis isolates specific binding	Image decomposition via non-negative matrix factorisation (NMF)	Support vector machine to produce probabilities score from little to no specific binding through to AD-like scans
Assumptions	Spatially synchronised accumulation according to the maximum amyloid carrying capacity of each region	Second principal component represents specific binding	First component represents specific binding	-
Range	% unbounded	-1 to 1 unbounded	0 to 100 0 and 100 are anchor points	% Bounded (or unbounded using a logit transform)
Reference region independent	No	No	No	Yes
MR independent	No	Yes (but No for training)	No	No
Specificity when processing scans from different tracers	Needs to match NS_K image scale (<i>Rizzo et al., 2020</i>)	Principal components specific to each tracer	NMF components specific to each tracer	Training on tracer specific datasets
Possible application for tau	Implemented (<i>Whittington and Gunn, 2021</i>)	Not implemented, comparable approach by <i>Cho et al., 2020</i>)	N/A	Not implemented
Validation	Against SUVR on ADNI (<i>Whittington and Gunn, 2019</i>) and GAAIN data (<i>Rizzo et al., 2020</i>)	Against SUVR, CSF, visual read and neuropathology on BioFINDER and ADNI data (<i>Leuzy et al., 2020, Lilja et al., 2019</i>)	Against standard CL on GAAIN and AIBL data (<i>Bourgeat et al., 2021</i>)	Against SUVR and CSF A β 42 using ADNI data
Availability	Available via Invicros's IQ Analytics Platform	Software freely available for research upon request	Open source https://doi.org/10.25919/5f8400a0b6a1e .	Plans to make it open source
Implementation in studies	<i>Zammit et al., 2019, 2021 (Zammit et al., 2021, Zammit et al., 2020)</i>	<i>Haller et al., 2021 (Haller et al., 2020)</i>	-	-
Main strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased sensitivity for longitudinal change in amyloid load - Implemented for all amyloid tracers (PiB (<i>Zammit et al., 2020</i>); ¹⁸F tracers (<i>Rizzo et al., 2020</i>)) - Implemented for tau (<i>Whittington and Gunn, 2021</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MR independent - Reference region independent - Software includes pre-processing - Fully automatic process (~20 seconds) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Robustness to change in tracer in a longitudinal setting - Improve longitudinal consistency compared to CL - Implemented for all amyloid tracers 	Reference region independent
Main limitations	Relies on a reference region	Relies on a reference region for training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relies on a reference region - Sub-optimal decomposition for ¹⁸F tracers 	Sensitivity to training set
Possible improvements	-	Allow for more principal components	Independence from MR using CapAIBL (<i>Bourgeat et al., 2018, Bourgeat et al., 2022</i>)	Independent from MR

Abbreviations - NS: non-specific; K: maximum amyloid carrying capacity; ADNI: Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative; AIBL: Australian Imaging Biomarkers and Lifestyle Study of Ageing; GAAIN: Global Alzheimer's Association Interactive Network; AMPSS: amyloid pattern similarity score; SUVR: standard uptake value ratio; CL: Centiloid scale; CSF: cerebrospinal fluid.

AIBL study was designed in part to determine the individual risk of developing AD, the time from symptom onset, as well as specific risk factors, for which healthy controls (HC; $N=69$), and subjects from the AD spectrum were recruited, including 118 subjects with subjective memory complaint (SMC), 64 with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), 17 with AD, and 9 with another diagnosis.

PET images were acquired for 20 minutes, starting at 90min after intravenous injection of approximately 185 MBq of [¹⁸F]flutemetamol. The AIBL data is a multi-centre study using several PET scanners: Allegro Body (Philips Medical Systems), Biograph128 (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen), Discovery (GE Medical Systems). Images were reconstructed iteratively via 3D RAMLA, 3D OSEM or VPHD algorithms respectively of their scanners, then smoothed with a 6mm Gaussian kernel. No partial volume correction was applied. The full study protocol is described elsewhere (*Ellis et al., 2009*). Images were then used as inputs for the image processing and analysis pipelines.

2.1.3. Test-retest data

2.1.3.1. [¹⁸F]florbetapir test-retest data (*Insight46 cohort*). Because there were no dedicated test-retest studies for [¹⁸F]florbetapir available, we identified individuals from Insight46 who are unlikely to accumulate A β over time as a proxy for test-rest [¹⁸F]florbetapir data, as in *Landau et al. (Landau et al., 2015)*. Subjects were included based on the following criteria: (1) both baseline and follow-up PET available (follow-up time: 2.4 ± 0.1 years), (2) CSF A β 42/40 and ptau181 available at follow-up, (3) at follow-up, CSF A β 42/40 value in the top quartile, (4) at follow-up, CSF ptau181 ≤ 57 pg/ml (cut-off from the manufacturer and further validated (*Keshavan et al., 2021*)), (5) no mild cognitive impairment or major brain disorder at baseline (based clinical consensus criteria (*Lu et al., 2019*)), yielding 16 individuals.

2.1.3.2. [¹⁸F]flutemetamol test-retest data (*independent cohorts*). Finally, 10 test-retest scans from subjects with an AD diagnosis acquired using

Table 2
Demographic characteristics for each dataset

	N Subjects (1 st timepoint)	Age (years)	Gender (% female)	ApoE4 $\epsilon 4$ (% carriers)	N Timepoints	Follow-up time	Radiotracer	Dynamic acquisition
Insight 46	350	70.6 \pm 0.7	48.9	29.3	2	2.4 \pm 0.2 years	^{18}F -florbetapir	yes
AIBL	277	73.4 \pm 5.9	51.6	30.4	3	fu1: 1.6 \pm 0.6 years fu2: 3.2 \pm 0.5 years	^{18}F -flutemetamol	no
Test-retest ^{18}F -florbetapir test-retest (Insight46 cohort)	16	70.5 \pm 0.6	25	-	2	2.4 \pm 0.1 years	^{18}F -florbetapir	yes
^{18}F -flutemetamol test-retest (independent cohort)	10	72.5 \pm 6.5	40.0	-	2	7 days or 1-4 weeks	^{18}F -flutemetamol	no

Where applicable, values are described as mean \pm standard deviation.

Abbreviations - ApoE $\epsilon 4$ carriers: carriers of at least one copy of the $\epsilon 4$ allele of the APOE gene; fu= follow-up.

^{18}F flutemetamol were also included (Vandenberghe et al., 2010, Miki et al., 2017).

The test-retest ^{18}F flutemetamol data was comprised of two ^{18}F flutemetamol studies: 5 subjects from a Japanese Phase II study (GE067-017) with scans acquired 1-4 weeks apart (Miki et al., 2017) and 5 subjects from a European Phase II study (ALZ201) with scans acquired 7 days apart (Vandenberghe et al., 2010). All subjects had a confirmed AD diagnosis. The 10 subjects were injected ~ 120 MBq of the tracer at each timepoint. PET images were acquired from ~ 90 min to 120min post injection (p.i.) (Miki et al., 2017) or ~ 85 min to 115min p.i. (Vandenberghe et al., 2010). PET scans were reconstructed into 6×5 min frames either iteratively or *via* filtered back projection depending on the scanner used. Images were smoothed with a 6mm Gaussian kernel. No partial volume correction was applied.

2.2. Image processing

2.2.1. Harmonised pre-processing

Except for the A β index which does not require any pre-processing, each of the amyloid metrics uses a slightly different pipeline. For a fairer comparison, we tried to harmonise these steps as much as possible. When required by the methodologies (see **Table S1**), the PET scans were registered into Montreal Neurologic Institute (MNI) 152 space (Mazziotta et al., 2001). First, ^{18}F florbetapir or ^{18}F flutemetamol scans were co-registered to the corresponding T1w MR using a rigid body transformation with the SPM 12 toolbox (Statistical Parametric Mapping, Wellcome Trust Centre for Neuroimaging, London, UK) (SPM12). Using diffeomorphic nonlinear registration tools (DARTEL) (Ashburner, 2007), the bias-corrected T1w scans were used to create a group average template that was then registered into MNI152 space. Finally, the DARTEL flow fields were applied (without modulation) to the PET data to register the scans into MNI152 space.

2.2.2. Conventional metrics

T1w images were parcellated with a multi-atlas based segmentation using geodesic information flow (GIF) (Cardoso et al., 2015). The labels were propagated to the PET scan through the transformation obtained from the PET-to-MR registration. CL values were computed with the whole cerebellum as reference region, as in the recommended processing guidelines (Klunk et al., 2015). SUVr was transformed into CL using the previously published calibration equations for test-retest ^{18}F flutemetamol (Battle et al., 2018) and Insight46 ^{18}F florbetapir data (Coath et al., 2022). We focused on CL values though SUVr results can be found in Supplementary material. The dynamic analysis was performed with tissue activity curves fitted using the reference Logan method (Logan et al., 1996) with a start time of 30 minutes, from which the distribution volume ratio (DVR) was derived. BP_{ND} is defined as $\text{DVR} - 1$. The mean time activity curve was obtained from the same composite ROI as used in the static analysis and with the cerebellar grey matter as the reference region.

2.2.3. Data-driven metrics

All data-driven metrics except for AMPSS and A β load used the training sets as laid out in the original papers. Specific processing requirements and implementation for the data-driven metrics can be found in Supplementary material.

2.3. Evaluation of the performance and statistical analysis

To evaluate the performance of these novel data-driven metrics against established metrics in the literature, we used the following criteria (1) repeatability and reliability; (2) strength of association with the BP_{ND} , which is considered to be closer to ground truth than other available metrics, (3) strength of association with the CL scale; (4) variability of the annualised rates of change and (5) sample size requirements to power a clinical trial aimed at detecting a 25% decrease in

Table 3
Repeatability and reliability of amyloid metrics evaluated on test-retest [¹⁸F]florbetapir data from a subset of Insight46 scans assumed to be stable over time (N=16, except for DVR: N=13), and on test-retest [¹⁸F]flutemetamol data from independent cohorts (N=10). Selection criteria for Insight46 stable group: (1) baseline and follow-up PET available, (2) CSF Aβ42/40 and ptau181 available at follow-up, (3) at follow-up, CSF Aβ42/40 value in the top quartile, (4) at follow-up, CSF ptau181 <=57 pg/ml, (5) no mild cognitive impairment or major brain disorder at baseline ICC and 95% confidence intervals (in brackets) estimates were calculated based on a mean-rating (k = 2), absolute-agreement and a 2-way mixed-effects model.

	¹⁸ F-florbetapir (Insight46 cohort)										¹⁸ F-flutemetamol (independent cohorts)									
	DVR (BP _{ND} + 1)	CL	Aβ load	Aβ index	CL _{NMF}	AMPSS	CL	Aβ load	Aβ index	CL _{NMF}	AMPSS	CL	Aβ load	Aβ index	CL _{NMF}	AMPSS				
Sample Mean	1.06	-6.74	0.17	-0.53	-2.39	0.25	97.96	0.94	0.21	106.32	0.84									
Sample SD	0.03	7.95	0.05	0.09	8.99	0.11	21.55	0.18	0.14	22.39	0.06									
RMS between subjects	0.05	11.25	0.08	0.13	12.72	0.16	30.48	0.26	0.20	31.66	0.09									
RMS within subjects	0.02	3.69	0.01	0.04	2.78	0.04	2.63	0.02	0.01	2.10	0.01									
ICC	0.81 [0.36, 0.94]	0.89 [0.69, 0.96]	0.97 [0.91, 0.99]	0.92 [0.76, 0.97]	0.95 [0.87, 0.98]	0.93 [0.80, 0.97]	0.99 [0.97, 1.00]	0.99 [0.96, 1.00]	1.00 [0.98, 1.00]	1.00 [0.98, 1.00]	0.99 [0.95, 1.00]									

Abbreviations – AD: Alzheimer’s disease; HC: healthy controls; RMS: root mean squares; ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient.

amyloid accumulation over 2 years. Statistical analyses were performed using R, version 4.0.4 (R Program for Statistical Computing) (R Core Team 2021).

2.3.1. Repeatability and reliability

Repeatability of both the data-driven metrics and conventional measures of amyloid burden were assessed according to the standard deviation between test and retest scans, decomposed into between-subject and within-subject components. These metrics have different ranges and various offsets, while being either bounded or not. Discrepancies in their mathematical definition hence restrict our ability to perform head-to-head comparisons.

The test-retest reliability was assessed using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) (Koo and Li, 2016). ICC estimates and their 95% confidence intervals were calculated using R irr package based on a mean-rating (k = 2), absolute-agreement and a 2-way mixed-effects model, which assumes the same measurement error at each timepoint.

Two of the cohorts in this study provided some capability for assessing reliability of the data-driven metrics. The first was a [¹⁸F]florbetapir test-retest dataset “built by selecting” 16 stable subjects from Insight46, and the second was the [¹⁸F]flutemetamol test-retest dataset (from independent cohorts) with 10 individuals with high amyloid burden and short interval between scans.

2.3.2. Correlation with BP_{ND}

No ground truth, such as histopathology, exists for *in vivo* quantification of amyloid burden, however, BP_{ND} obtained from dynamic acquisitions using kinetic modelling accounts for variations in physiological factors such as blood flow alterations and radiotracer clearance (Schmidt et al., 2015, van Berckel et al., 2013). These advantages provide a more accurate representation of the true measurements of specific amyloid binding compared to the SUVR. We therefore computed the repeated measurement correlation between each data-driven metric and the BP_{ND}. The repeated measurement correlation (implemented in the R package rmcrr) was chosen to take into consideration the non-independence of the measures obtained for the same individual over time (Bakdash and Marusch, 2017). It does so by shifting the common use of analysis of variance (ANOVA) and using it to determine the relationship between two continuous variables (amyloid metrics at baseline and follow-up) while controlling for between-subject variance. From this atypical ANOVA implementation can be derived a repeated measurement correlation coefficient (r_{rm}), which here represents the within-person change in one metric versus the BP_{ND}, and is defined as follows:

$$r_{rm} = \sqrt{\frac{SS_{measure}}{SS_{measure} + SS_{error}}}$$

with SS_{measure} and SS_{error} representing the sum of squares of the measures and errors respectively.

95% confidence intervals for r_{rm} were built using 2,000 bootstrap replicates. This was only evaluated in the Insight46 dataset, as the AIBL data acquisitions included only late static frames.

2.3.3. Correlation with CL

The repeated measurement correlation of each metric with CL values was also evaluated, as it allows for the comparison of [¹⁸F]flutemetamol (AIBL) and [¹⁸F]florbetapir (Insight46) data. In each case, the strength of the association was determined by the repeated measurement correlation r_{rm}. 95% confidence intervals for r_{rm} were built using 2,000 bootstrap replicates. The CL scale being developed to harmonise amyloid measurements across tracers, we would not expect to observe a significant difference in longitudinal change across metrics.

2.3.4. Annualised rates of change

For Insight46, the annualised rates of changes (ARC) were computed

Fig. 2. Bland-Altman plots indicating bias between test and retest measurements. Dashed lines indicate the mean, lower and upper limit of agreement (± 1.96 standard deviation from the mean).

as the difference between follow-up and baseline metric over the time interval between scans. As the AIBL data comprises a subset of subjects with three timepoints ($N=119$), the amyloid accumulation rates were estimated with linear mixed effects models (LME; using the *lme4* package in R). We included both random slopes and random intercepts to account for inter-individual variability, with an unstructured covariance matrix allowing for a covariance between the slope and intercept. With dt representing the time since the baseline scans in years, the LME model was as follows:

$$y_{i,j} = \beta_{0,i} + \beta_{1,i}t_{i,j} + e_{i,j}$$

with, $e_{i,j} \sim N(0, \sigma_e^2)$, for $i \neq k$, $cov(u_i, u_k) = 0$, $cov(e_{i,j}, u_j) = 0$

Here $y_{i,j}$ is the value of the outcome variable (i.e., amyloid metric) for the i^{th} subject, attending their j^{th} PET acquisition ($j = 1$ to 3). $\beta_{0,i} = \beta_0 + u_{0,i}$ and $\beta_{1,i} = \beta_1 + u_{1,i}$ with β_0 and β_1 the overall fixed effects for the intercept and the slope, and $u_{0,i}$ and $u_{1,i}$ the random effects for the intercept and the slope at the group level such that $\begin{pmatrix} u_{0,i} \\ u_{1,i} \end{pmatrix} \sim N\left(0, \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_0^2 & \sigma_{01} \\ \sigma_{01} & \sigma_1^2 \end{pmatrix}\right)$.

$e_{i,j}$ is the random effect at the individual level and $t_{i,j}$ the time of the j^{th} PET acquisition relative to the time of the baseline acquisition (in years). The corresponding R syntax is: 'Metric ~ dt + (1 + dt|subject)'. In some cases, this model would not converge due to the inability of estimating the random slope effect in the amyloid negative population. In these instances, a random intercept only model was used for the amyloid negative group. The previous equation can be simplified with $\beta_{1,i} = \beta_1$, $u_{0,i} \sim N(0, \sigma_0^2)$ and the R syntax is then: 'Metric ~ dt + (1 | subject)'. Additionally, coefficients of variation for the ARC were computed (standard deviation/mean), with the sampling uncertainty assessed using bootstrap resampling. Bias-corrected and accelerated confidence intervals were obtained using 5,000 bootstrap replicates.

2.3.5. Sample size estimates

Finally, the ARC and standard deviations were used to compute the sample size estimates ($\alpha = 0.05$; $1-\beta = 80\%$) required to detect 25%

Fig. 3. Correlation between amyloid metrics and non-displaceable binding potential BP_{ND} , evaluated with dynamic acquisition scans from Insight46 data. The 95% confidence interval for r_m was built using 2,000 bootstrap replicates. The dotted lines represent the regression for the metrics averaged per subject. Abbreviation - r_m : repeated measurement correlation coefficient.

Fig. 4. Correlation between amyloid metrics and the Centiloid scale (CL). The dotted lines represent the regression for the metrics averaged per subject. The 95% confidence interval for r_{rm} was built using 2,000 bootstrap replicates.

decrease in annualised amyloid accumulation. The sample size estimates represent the required sample size per arm, in the context of a trial with one measure of change and equal number of participants in each arm. As in Lopes Alves et al. (Lopes Alves et al., 2021), we designed two clinical trial scenarios, based on CL cut-off values. The first is a secondary prevention trial with individuals in early amyloid accumulation or pre-clinical AD ($20 \leq CL \leq 50$ at baseline) (Aisen et al., 2020). The second is a secondary prevention trial with individuals with at least intermediate amyloid load ($CL > 20$ at baseline). Non-parametric, bias-corrected, and accelerated confidence intervals were estimated using 5,000 bootstrap replicates.

3. Results

3.1. Repeatability and reliability

A summary of our results on the repeatability and reliability of each metric can be found in Table 3.

The [¹⁸F]flutemetamol test-retest data represents short-interval acquisitions in 10 subjects with an AD diagnosis, while the [¹⁸F]florbetapir data was a much longer scan interval in a subset of individuals that represented a stable group of 16 healthy controls. Test and retest scans acquired with [¹⁸F]flutemetamol show higher agreement with each other than the ones in [¹⁸F]florbetapir subset (Fig. 2).

Repeatability can only be compared for the CL and CL_{NMF} as they are on a similar scale. Both in the [¹⁸F]flutemetamol and [¹⁸F]florbetapir data, the within-subject RMS of these two metrics is within 1 unit. Furthermore, we can assess dependent reliability of all metrics against

each other as the ICC is not dependent on the range of the metric. For the [¹⁸F]flutemetamol test-retest scans, we observed excellent reliability of all the metrics ($ICC \geq 0.98$), which indicates that the variability observed between the two scans is mostly attributable to an underlying difference in protein deposition across individuals rather than measurement error. The overlapping confidence intervals suggest that there is no evidence of difference in this across methods. For [¹⁸F]florbetapir, our results suggest that all metrics have acceptable reliability. We verified using an *F* test that the high ICC values could not be explained by high between-subject variability.

3.2. Correlation with BP_{ND}

Repeated measure correlations between BP_{ND} and the other metrics were computed for the Insight46 dataset (only dataset with dynamic acquisitions) and are shown in Fig. 3. There is a positive association between the longitudinal change in all metrics and BP_{ND}, with highest r_{rm} values for the CL, Aβ load and Aβ index. Correlations between the novel metrics and the SUVr can be found in Supplementary material.

3.3. Correlation with CL

Comparison of the data-driven metrics with the CL scale over both datasets is shown in Fig. 4. The CL_{NMF}, Aβ load and Aβ index show close regression slopes for both AIBL and Insight46. The r_{rm} is highest for these three metrics indicating a high association with longitudinal change in CL especially in Insight46, although a lower r_{rm} for the Aβ index in AIBL. All data-driven metrics systematically show higher correlation with CL

Table 4

Annualised rates of change in amyloid deposition and coefficients of variation in AIBL and Insight46 datasets. Values are described as mean ± standard deviation. Bias corrected and accelerated confidence intervals for the coefficients of variation were built via bootstrap resampling using 5,000 replicates. Abbreviations – ARC: annualised rates of change, CV: coefficients of variation

	Insight46				AIBL					
	ARC				CV	ARC				CV
	All	CL ≤ 15	20 ≤ CL ≤ 50	CL > 20		All	CL ≤ 15	20 ≤ CL ≤ 50	CL > 20	
<i>N</i>	438	331	39	67	438	185	100	11	52	185
BP _{ND}	0.01 ± 0.02	0.01 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.02	1.6 [1.3, 2.2]	N/A				
CL	2.4 ± 3.5	1.5 ± 2.8	6.1 ± 3.8	5.5 ± 3.5	1.5 [1.3, 1.7]	0.5 ± 13.8	-0.1 ± 12.5	3.0 ± 13.4	2.4 ± 15.7	26.8 [8.7, >100]
Aβ load	0.01 ± 0.02	0.01 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.01	1.7 [1.4, 2.0]	0.01 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.03	0.02 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.05	2.9 [2.3, 3.7]
Aβ index	0.01 ± 0.03	0.01 ± 0.03	0.04 ± 0.03	0.04 ± 0.03	2.2 [1.8, 3.2]	0.02 ± 0.08	0.01 ± 0.04	0.04 ± 0.14	0.03 ± 0.09	3.6 [2.7, 6.3]
CL _{NMF}	2.1 ± 3.0	1.2 ± 2.3	5.9 ± 3.1	5.2 ± 2.8	1.5 [1.3, 1.8]	2.4 ± 5.6	1.6 ± 5.6	3.6 ± 4.2	3.5 ± 5.5	2.4 [2.0, 3.0]
AMPSS	0.02 ± 0.04	0.02 ± 0.04	0.04 ± 0.05	0.04 ± 0.05	1.9 [1.6, 2.4]	0.01 ± 0.11	0.01 ± 0.11	0.03 ± 0.07	0.02 ± 0.11	12.9 [4.6, >100]

Table 5

Sample size estimates per arm ($\alpha = 0.05$; $1 - \beta = 80\%$) required to detect a 25% decrease in annualized amyloid accumulation. This assumes two arms, one treatment and one placebo with equal size. Two scenarios were assessed: a secondary prevention trial focusing on early accumulators ($20 < CL \leq 50$), and a secondary prevention trial for individuals with at least moderate amyloid burden ($CL \geq 20$). Bias-corrected and accelerated confidence intervals were obtained using 5,000 bootstrap replicates.

	Insight46	
	$20 \leq CL \leq 50$	$CL > 20$
<i>N</i>	39	67
BP_{ND}	93 [39, 340]	105 [52, 284]
CL	96 [56, 183]	117 [69, 232]
A β load	81 [52, 139]	111 [69, 208]
A β index	131 [69, 288]	147 [84, 348]
CL_{NMF}	71 [45, 113]	74 [52, 109]
AMPSS	558 [220, 3123]	553 [217, 3069]

Abbreviations – cgm: cerebellar grey matter reference region; whc: whole cerebellum reference region.

in Insight46 compared to AIBL.

3.4. Annual rate of change & coefficients of variation

The annualised amyloid accumulation rates were computed for all metrics in Insight46 and AIBL, for three subsets of the datasets defined using the baseline CL value of each subject (Table 4). The ability to compare these ARC in between metrics is restricted by the various ranges of these methodologies as well as the different cognitive profiles of the subjects in the Insight46 and AIBL studies. Nonetheless, we can observe that the ARC variability is from two and up to eight times higher in the AIBL dataset compared to the Insight46 dataset. In Insight46, the coefficients of variation of the ARC for the CL_{NMF} and the A β load were in line with the ones from the conventional metrics while in AIBL, these two metrics had a lower CV compared to the CL. The mean CL ARC was found to be negative in AIBL in the subset of scans with $CL \leq 15$.

3.5. Sample size estimates

The sample size estimates to detect a 25% reduction in accumulation rates are summarised in Table 5. For secondary prevention trials scenarios, targeting early accumulators and subjects with at least moderate amyloid burden, the CL_{NMF} consistently displayed lower sample size requirements in comparison to all other metrics, though the confidence intervals do overlap between measures. The A β load performed in line with the BP_{ND} and the CL approaches.

4. Discussion

In this study, we evaluated four novel data-driven metrics of amyloid deposition on three datasets, acquired with [^{18}F]florbetapir and [^{18}F]flutemetamol, and compared them to the more established model-based values including CL and BP_{ND} .

We first evaluated the repeatability and reliability of the data-driven methodologies. The variability of repeated measurements should be considered together with the mean, standard deviation, and range of each metric. Indeed, a direct comparison between these metrics is not always possible because of the different scales and ranges of these novel measures. No difference in ICC between metrics was observable in the test-retest [^{18}F]flutemetamol and [^{18}F]florbetapir data, except for the DVR which had a slightly lower ICC and greater confidence interval than all other metrics. This might be explained by small between-subject variability with the DVR (rather than high within-subject variability), as a result of DVR values across amyloid negative individuals being very similar (around 1.0-1.1). This result between-subject in the within-subject variation being almost as high as the between subject

variation, which in turn decreases the ICC.

Repeated measure correlations between the amyloid metrics and the BP_{ND} (DVR - 1) suggest that the longitudinal trajectories of the CL, A β index, A β load and CL_{NMF} are close to those of the BP_{ND} .

When examining the association between these data-driven metrics with the well-established CL scale, we found strong cross-sectional relationships between the CL_{NMF} , A β load and A β index across both of our main datasets. AMPSS, on the other hand, showed a more divergent relationship between the two datasets, suggesting that it could be dependent on the training set used. In our case, we withheld part of the original dataset to form the training data, hence differences in the original dataset might be reflected on the final AMPSS. While there are similar relationships between datasets, all metrics show a noticeably higher association to longitudinal intra-individual change in CL in the Insight46 dataset compared to AIBL. This could be explained by the definition of the r_m coefficient as it may be unstable in cases where the expected slope across subjects varies significantly, and in cases where the number of observations per subject differs. These two factors would be more prominent in AIBL compared to Insight46, which is mostly comprised of cognitively unimpaired subjects who underwent two PET scans. Additionally, differences in the type of scanner used between these datasets could result in slightly different observed uptake in the reference region. The Insight 46 uses a single Siemens Biograph combined PET-MR scanner, which tends to be more modern than many of the PET-CT scanners used in AIBL, as well as having a larger axial field of view. Another explanation could be that the Insight 46 cohort comprises mostly healthy controls while the linear regression for AIBL has more individuals, given the inclusion of MCI and AD patients, having higher amyloid values.

Finally, our results show that the BP_{ND} , CL_{NMF} and A β load are the metrics that are the most sensitive to changes in amyloid accumulation rate, leading to lower coefficients of variation and lower sample size estimates required to power hypothetical secondary prevention trials. We chose not to include the sample size estimates for AIBL (where the sample sizes were also lowest for the CL_{NMF} and A β load) because there was no evidence for many of the metrics, data-driven or established, of the ARC being significantly different from zero, which appears to be driven more by a high level of longitudinal variability. This variability might stem from differences in uptake values in the cerebellum at each timepoint, that are dependent on the patient positioning within the scanner field of view. Some approaches rely on an accurate definition and registration of the cerebellum or cerebellar grey matter to build their image component templates from which the data-driven metrics are derived. Under- or over-estimation of the amyloid burden in the cerebellum might therefore increase the longitudinal variability across all metrics. Overall, the CL_{NMF} and A β load seem to offer a more precise alternative to the established CL, though further studies on larger cohorts that also include [^{18}F]florbetaben are required for confirmation.

Beyond quantitative performance criteria, several of the data-driven metrics provide other potential benefits that should be taken into consideration. As mentioned previously, the AMPSS and the A β index do not require a pre-defined reference region which is regularly subject of debate and a well-documented source of uncertainty. For the AMPSS, as the original training consisted of F-18 florbetapir PET data from ADNI, we first attempted to use this training data for the F-18 flutemetamol AIBL dataset as well, but the poor performance of the SVM suggests that the voxel-wise multivariate pattern captured by the training is tracer-specific (data not shown). For unseen data, the optimisation of a well-calibrated unbiased, cross-tracer training set could potentially increase the accuracy and precision of this metric. There may be instances, such as individuals with contraindications to MR, where PET-only methods are desirable. The A β index and an updated version of the CL_{NMF} do not require an MR, and can be alternatives to PET-only pipelines that were developed for the SUVr and CL (Bourgeat et al., 2015; Iaccarino et al., 2022). The A β load can also be computed without MR, provided that the NS and K templates are available and that SUVr maps are obtained with

a PET-only pipeline. Moreover, the availability of the software is important to consider towards the aims of reproducibility and open science. If the software to perform the data-driven metric includes all pre-processing steps, or alternatively documentation that is suitably comprehensive such that these steps can be accurately reproduced in other user's environments, then the variability caused by using various pipelines (and in particular, the registration software) could be limited. Indeed, we found that the A β index was the metric which performs most similarly across both our datasets in terms of correlation with CL (cross-sectional data only). Importantly, the CL_{NMF}, like the CL, is tracer independent and was shown to be more robust than CL to change in tracer in the original paper (Bourgeat et al., 2021). The improved precision of the CL_{NMF} could further encourage the use of Centiloid and standardised scales by establishing a harmonised outcome metric for clinical practice, and by being key to several stages of drug development (Pemberton et al., 2022). Lastly, it is worth noting that the A β index, the AMPSS and the CL_{NMF} are either open-source or available to researchers upon request.

These novel metrics, being data-driven, may help us gain insight into the spatiotemporal pattern of amyloid accumulation. The A β index, A β load and CL_{NMF} that isolate the specific binding pattern, and the AMPSS that dichotomises A β accumulation between HC and AD, overall show relatively close performance compared to the SUVR. This would suggest that for a large proportion of the population, there is a multivariate pattern of amyloid uptake rather than a regional spreading pattern. This supports a relatively generalisable global multivariate pattern of uptake, where some regions accumulate faster than others. This is line with the work of Whittington and Gunn (Whittington et al., 2018) and Cho that showed that amyloid accumulation occurs simultaneously across many regions in the brain, usually by the time tau deposition in the entorhinal cortex emerges (Cho et al., 2020).

Data-driven metrics also present with some limitations. They are all surrogate measures of amyloid deposition and usually compress spatial information into a single summary metric. It is nonetheless worth noting that two methodologies can also help image amyloid patterns: the AMPSS which can output a feature weighted map from the SVM and the A β load which computation requires a SUVR fitted image from the NS and K maps. We could however take advantage of specific spatial patterns to target specific populations. For instance, subjects with cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) have shown significant amyloid uptake in the occipital cortex (Sperling et al., 2011). A data-driven approach could potentially isolate a component specific to CAA, allowing the discrimination of two types of amyloid deposition. Finally, as these methods are data-driven and more susceptible to bias, demographic characteristics and technical specificities should be considered before implementing them on novel datasets.

There are potential limitations with regards to our implementation of each method. We chose to process the scans with little or no modification to the methods, including using the training and calibration data provided for each method where available. Although these methods are all data-driven, the training and calibration datasets differed in the number of scans required, amyloid burden distribution in the dataset and spatial and intensity normalisation parameters. The use of different training and calibration sets unique to each data-driven metric is another potential source of variability. On the these hand, our approach avoids overfitting and allowed us to evaluate the methods how they will most likely be implemented by other researchers and clinicians. Furthermore, the training set for the A β load from which the NS and K maps are derived was made of [¹⁸F]florbetapir scans and is therefore not best suited for the AIBL study acquired with [¹⁸F]flutemetamol. Despite the data-driven metrics being less reliant on formal anatomical boundaries to define a specific reference or target region, most implementations of these metrics still involve some reference region definition as part of the process, and the choice of reference region is different between methods.

Apart from the four metrics evaluated in this study, other data-driven

methods have been developed. The AMYQ method by Pegueroles et al. (Pegueroles et al., 2021) is similar to the A β index in that it relies on a PCA approach and does not require the definition of a reference region. The idea of the adaptive template created via PCA in the A β index has also been achieved using MR independent deep learning approach by Kang et al. (Kang et al., 2018) Another A β load was implemented by Tanaka et al. (Tanaka et al., 2020), which mainly differs from the A β load by Whittington and Gunn in the creation of K and NS templates, for which they use a PCA. Defining a metric without a formally defined reference region was also the goal of Chincarini et al., who developed ELBA, a metric of amyloid deposition relying on the intensity distribution patterns rather than specific ROIs. (Chincarini et al., 2016) Finally, Liu et al. proposed a method to estimate the specific amyloid burden (SA β load) relying on the estimate of the non-specific binding using deep learning (Liu et al., 2021).

4.1. Future directions

The methods examined seem to be able to capture population-level, longitudinal, patterns of amyloid deposition. Further investigation assessing their capacity to accurately measure the change in protein burden at the subject level would be clinically relevant. To implement these metrics in a longitudinal setting, their robustness to different tracers and scanners with different spatial resolution, as often is the case in multi-centre studies, should be investigated. Future evaluation could also include [¹⁸F]florbetaben data which was not tested our study, as well as novel tau metrics which were beyond the scope of this study.

Overall, the recent drive to develop innovative, alternative methods to measure protein deposition via PET might benefit from a formal challenge in the future where these methods are evaluated against an unseen reference dataset that each group processes and provides results on.

5. Conclusion

We evaluated and validated four types of data-driven metrics of amyloid deposition on three separate datasets using a joint set of criteria against the more established CL and BP_{ND}. We found A β index, A β load and CL_{NMF} all have a close longitudinal association with the BP_{ND}, while the CL_{NMF} and A β load could offer a more precise alternative to the CL. Moreover, these novel data-driven metrics can provide benefits such as being robust across tracers and pre-processing pipelines while offering a precision comparable or superior to the CL. Reducing the variability of PET longitudinal measurements may be achieved by using data-driven metrics of amyloid uptake.

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Data-code availability statement

The Centiloid calibration datasets can be downloaded at <http://www.gaain.org/centiloid-project>.

The AIBL data can be downloaded through LONI after registration at <http://adni.loni.usc.edu/category/aibl-study-data/>.

The Insight46 data is a sub-study of the National Survey of Health and Development (NSHD). The data sharing statement for NSHD can be found at <https://nshd.mrc.ac.uk/data-sharing/>.

The A β index can be made available to researchers.

The python code used to build the NMF models as well as the NMF models can be downloaded from <https://doi.org/10.25919/5f8400a0b6a1e>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ariane Bollack: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Pawel J Markiewicz:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Alle Meije Wink:** Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Lloyd Prosser:** Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Johan Lilja:** Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Pierrick Bourgeat:** Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Jonathan M Schott:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **William Coath:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Lyduine E Collij:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Hugh G Pemberton:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Gill Farrar:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Frederik Barkhof:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **David M Cash:** Supervision, Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

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Supplementary materials

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